

MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURE-BATTERY MARINE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The multifunctional composites developed in this work use traditional fiber reinforced marine composites for structure function and rechargeable lithium polymer cells to provide energy storage and structure function. Three structure-battery configurations were designed, fabricated and tested. Mechanical stiffness and strength in flexure, energy storage capacities, and buoyancy levels are reported.

Keywords: lithium polymer battery, energy storage, unmanned vehicle

INTRODUCTION

Various subsystems in marine applications, especially unmanned underwater vehicles, compete for space. Multifunctional design seeks to improve system performance through the physical integration of different subsystem functionalities. In the case of marine systems such as unmanned underwater vehicles (UUVs), endurance is a key system performance metric. There is interest in enhancing the endurance time of UUVs through the use of hybrid power subsystems consisting of fuel cells for cruise-mode and batteries for sprint-mode portions of a mission. In existing electric-powered UUVs, the power subsystem consisting of batteries resides within the hull and competes for space with payload. The hybrid fuel-cell/battery power systems use much of the available volume for fuel-oxidizer storage. Space can be freed-up within the UUV power section for additional fuel-oxidizer or additional payload by relocating existing battery cells into skin and/or other structural components.

The idea of integrating energy storage and generation elements into structure for system performance improvement is being addressed by many researchers. Most recently, Liu et al. have designed lithium polymer batteries with tunable mechanical properties from elastic to structurally rigid based on a high molecular weight PVDF

matrix [1]. Along the same lines, in a series of paper Pereira et al. have measured the electrical performance of batteries under tension, which were composed of embedded thin-film cells in carbon fiber-reinforced polymers [2-3]. Similar to the strategy adopted in [1], Wetzel and coworkers have designed, fabricated and mechanically tested inherently multifunctional structural batteries and capacitors [4-6]. Beside evaluating batteries as energy storage components, researchers have quantified various carbon fibers, fabrics and papers by experimentally measuring their electrochemical capacity, capacitance and mechanical strength [7]. There have also been attempts to combine energy harvesting and energy storage components in hybrid multifunctional systems. In one study, the present authors performed a multifunctional feasibility study of energy scavenging systems, based on solar, wind, thermal, electromagnetic and autophagous (self-consuming) sources for small-scale unmanned systems, by suggesting potential designs and analyzing their components for structural potential [8]. Pereira et al. have taken one step further by actually embedding energy harvesting thin-film solar cells with solid-state lithium polymer cells into carbon fiber-reinforced composite matrix with reasonable success [9].

In previous work on structure-battery (SB) composites, the present authors have presented a multifunctional design framework based on material-architecture performance indices [10]. They have also proposed designs and estimated their performance for application in small scale UAVs [11-12]. These composites were made of traditional fiber reinforced polymer layers to provide structure function, and rechargeable lithium polymer battery cells to provide both energy storage and structure function. In [10], they also showed that SB implementation in UAVs can increase the available energy and/or decrease system weight depending on the details of the design.

In this work, the focus is on the design, fabrication and performance characterization of multifunctional structure-battery (SB) composite materials for application in unmanned underwater vehicle (UUV) systems. In contrast to small-scale airborne applications, structural composites for marine applications are more concerned with volume and buoyancy than weight. There are additional concerns related to structural degradation and galvanic corrosion (metal contact with carbon fibers) in seawater operational environments along with the need for water-tight connections and electrical isolation. All unmanned vehicle systems can be exposed to a range of structural loads: axial, flexural, torsional/shear, and low-velocity impact. However, UUVs are also exposed to potentially large (hydrostatic) pressure loads when operating at ocean depths (~10 kPa per meter depth).

The SB composites described herein also use traditional fiber reinforced layers to provide structure function and rechargeable lithium polymer battery cells to provide both energy storage and structure function. Design objectives for the composites developed in this work include: 1) volumetric energy density of 50 Wh/L or greater, and similar or better: 2) flexure properties, 3) buoyancy levels, and 4) dimensions relative to their traditional (unifunctional) marine composite counterparts. Unifunctional marine composites are either fiber reinforced polymer laminates, or fiber reinforced polymer face-sheets/foam core sandwich designs for enhanced bending performance and buoyancy. Both of these fundamental configurations (laminates and sandwich) are considered in this work. Laminates are used as skin, casing, and bulkheads, and sandwich composites are used in structural frame components and skins. The reinforcements are carbon- and glass-fibers or woven cloth. Thin layers of fiberglass are typically used on the exterior surfaces of carbon-epoxy composites to provide electrical

insulation and prevent galvanic corrosion on contact with metals in seawater (carbon is extremely noble in the galvanic series). The core materials are either a closed-cell foam or syntactic foam depending upon the targeted depth rating.

The paper starts with description of the materials selection, composites design and fabrication processes, and experimental characterization procedures. Mechanical and electrical performance of fabricated specimens follow in the section on results. A discussion of the test results with a comparison between unifunctional and multifunctional performance is next followed by conclusions.

METHOD

Materials

High-performance marine carbon- and glass-epoxy materials (prepregs and wet layup) from SP Gurit were used in the fabrication of all specimens. In the case of carbon fibers, 2x2 twill-weave fabrics, RC416T and XC411, were used in prepregs and wet layup, respectively. The RE295 twill-weave glass fabric was used for electrical isolation purposes in both prepreg and wet layup form. The prepregs use the SE84LV resin (80 deg C cure), and the wet layups use the Ampreg 22 resin (50 deg C cure). Prime 20LV epoxy was used to pot the battery cells into the foam channels. S-1800 SAN closed-cell foam was used for framing the battery cells and as a buoyant core material. Adhesive bonding with Spabond 345 (50 deg C cure) was used to join the various component layers together in the final SB composite assembly process.

Kokam USA rechargeable lithium polymer cells (type SLPB 356495; 3.7 mm x 64 mm x 95 mm) were used as the energy-storage elements. These cells are nominally rated at 3.7 V and 2100 mAh, weigh ~42 gm with packaging, and have an operating temperature range of -20 to 60 deg C. Short term storage as high as 80 deg C is possible with only slight degradation in energy capacity.

Design

Three structure-battery (SB) composite beam prototype designs were developed to assess the technology's potential for underwater marine applications (Figure 1). The first is a SB Laminate beam with commercial lithium polymer cells “framed” within closed-cell foam channels and then bonded between a flat laminate on one side, and a conformal laminate on the other side. The second design is a Modular SB Stiffener beam with cells framed in a foam channel that is bonded between a thin flat laminate on one side (structural attachment side) and a thicker conformal laminate on the other side. The third is a SB Sandwich beam with cells embedded in the foam core at the center of the specimen (i.e., approximately along the neutral axis). The SB Laminate and SB Sandwich designs are intended to serve as replacements for existing marine structural components (e.g., skin and frame). The Modular SB Stiffener is intended to serve as a structural stiffener for redesigned (less substantial) structural components (e.g., skin). The “modular” implies reversible bonding capability for easy removal and replacement (e.g., battery failure). Composite laminate, [G,C₈,G], and sandwich [G,C₄,foam,C₄,G] specimens without embedded cells (unifunctional designs) have also been fabricated to provide a baseline for comparing mechanical performance.

Each SB composite utilizes braided copper wiring for power bussing. Epoxy-glass plies are utilized as facing layers for the foam-cell cores to provide electrical insulation and on the exterior surfaces to prevent possible galvanic corrosion effects. The low density foam cell frames are sized to compensate for the higher density of the

cells and wiring. The foam/cells/wiring combinations are neutrally buoyant in the SB Laminate and Modular SB Stiffener configurations. The foam frames also serve as location templates for the cells/wiring during fabrication. The SB composite prototypes have either two or three embedded cells, depending upon the design, wired in parallel. The nominal output voltage is 3.7 V (same as the individual cells) and a total capacity of n times the cell-capacity (2.1 Ah), where n is the number of cells in parallel.

Fabrication

Fabrication steps requiring temperature excursions above 60 deg C (upper limit on cell temperature for zero capacity degradation) were performed before the addition of the cells. For example, all of the flat laminate component layers were fabricated using the prepreg materials with autoclave curing for 12 hours at 80 deg C with vacuum bagging and 40 psig external pressure. The foam frames were bonded in place using the SPABOND 345 adhesive. The conformal component layers were fabricated using a wet layup with the Ampreg 22 (50 deg C cure). All fabrication steps with cells involved were performed using the low temperature (50 deg C) curing epoxies and adhesives.

In preparation for assembly, the as-received lithium polymer cells were fully charged and then discharged to 25% state-of-charge. The outer covering of the cell's packaging is nylon. To ensure good bonding, the cells were plasma etched and dip-coated in the PRIME 20LV epoxy resin to form a protected bondable surface coating prior to epoxy potting in the foam frames. The power bussing consisted of 12 AWG braided/tinned copper; 18 AWG braided/tinned copper leads were soldered to the cell terminals and to the power bus leads with strain relief folds. Photographs of fabricated SB specimens are shown in Figures 2-4. Average dimensions of the specimens are given in Table 1, and additional fabrication details can be found in [13-14].

Experiments

Flexure testing of the unifunctional and multifunctional specimens was performed to characterize mechanical bending performance (i.e., stiffness and strength). Ragone testing of the multifunctional specimens, which measures energy storage capacity as a function of power discharge rate, was also conducted to characterize electrical performance.

Three-point bend (flexure) testing was performed on the multifunctional and unifunctional specimens to determine their apparent bending stiffness, $(EI)_{app}$, and the bending failure load, P_{bf} . The stiffness testing was conducted using a long-beam flexure fixture (Wyoming Test Fixtures; three-point bending with 350 mm span) on an MTS Insight 100 test system with a 10kN load cell and an contact deflectometer (0-12 mm travel) measuring specimen deflection under the load application point at mid-span. Strength testing was performed using the same loading fixture and test system. A 100 kN load cell was required for testing the sandwich configurations (both unifunctional and SB), and displacement of the specimens was measured at mid-span under the load application point using a large travel extensometer (MTS XLT; 0-970 mm displacement with optical encoded measurement) with one arm attached at the bottom of the specimen under the load application point at mid-span and the other arm attached to the bend fixture ("mechanical ground"). SEM "pin stub mounts" with double-sided adhesive on the mount face were bonded to the specimens and bend fixture to provide

attachment to the extensometer. In all of the tests, the crosshead displacement rate, $\dot{\delta}$, was adjusted to achieve an outer-fiber strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}$, of 0.0004 m/m/min using:

$$\dot{\delta} = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}L^2}{6h} \quad (1)$$

where L is the span (350 mm) and h is the specimen thickness (mm).

All of the stiffness measurements were conducted in the elastic regime; the applied deflections were limited to one-quarter or less of the predicted failure deflection corresponding to tensile failure of the fiberglass outer-layer on each specimen. All specimens were tested at least twice (once in each orientation, face-up, face-down). Owing to the non-flat conformal surfaces, the integrated SB specimens had 6.35 mm thick butyl rubber added between the specimen and fixture load pads when in contact with the uneven upper surface. Load-deflection data were recorded at 10 Hz during the test and then averaged (either 100 or 50 points per average) to create load-deflection data (at least twenty data points per test) for use in slope analysis and plotting. Apparent bending stiffness was determined using least-squares fitting of a line to a section of the averaged load-displacement curve; using the slope of the load-displacement curve, it is given by:

$$(EI)_{app} = \frac{L^3}{48} \frac{dP}{d\delta} \quad (2)$$

The data regions over which the slope $dP/d\delta$ was calculated were arbitrarily selected to correspond to the first linear region beyond the initial load-displacement “toe-region.” This encompasses data in the strain region from 0.4 to 1.4 $\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$ for the unifunctional sandwich, SB sandwich, and SB integrated laminate specimens, 0.1 to 0.6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$ for the modular SB stiffener specimens, with and without added laminate (i.e. skin), and 0.2 to 0.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$ for the unifunctional laminate specimens.

Strength measurements were conducted on two specimens for each unifunctional and SB configuration. Load-deflection data were recorded at 1 Hz during the test. The failure loads are identified as the maximum load achieved during testing.

For Ragone capacity testing, the cells were charged using commercial power-supplies/chargers with automatic CC (constant current) to CV (constant voltage) crossover. The SB composites were charged at 2100 mAh, corresponding to a C/2 rate for the SB Laminate and Modular SB Stiffener configurations (two 2100 mAh cells per specimen) or C/3 rate for the SB Sandwich configuration (three 2100 mAh cells per specimen). Energy storage capacity was characterized using constant-current discharge tests at four discharge rates (C/4, C/2, 1C and 2C) using an Agilent 6060B electronic load controlled by a LabView program. The discharge was terminated when the measured voltage dropped to 3.0 V. Ragone curves (volumetric: energy density vs. power density; and gravimetric: specific energy vs. specific power) were determined via integration of power (voltage times current) over time.

RESULTS

Figure 5 shows representative load-deflection plots for the Unifunctional Laminate and Modular SB Stiffener with Skin used to determine bending stiffness. The apparent bending stiffness of the Modular SB laminate is $\sim 7.7x$ greater than that of its unifunctional laminate counterpart. Apparent bending stiffness values for all specimen configurations are given in Table 2.

Figure 6 shows the load-deflection plots from the strength testing for the specimens categorized as either Laminate and Sandwich configuration. In the laminate configuration, the unifunctional laminate exhibits a much lower stiffness and loading carrying capacity. It had not failed on reaching 45 mm of deflection. One way of achieving failure with the given setup is to decrease the span setting to something less than 350 mm; that is being done in ongoing work. The other two (SB) laminates exhibit similar stiffnesses, but the failure load for the Modular SB is much larger (~2.3x) than that of the SB Laminate. For the sandwich configurations, both types (uni- and SB) exhibit similar stiffness, but the Uni-Sandwich specimens have a much larger failure load (~2.3x) than the SB Sandwich specimens. Measured failure loads for each tested specimens are given in Table 2, and photographs of specimen failures (representative) are shown in Figure 8. The Uni-Sandwich specimens failed by compression overload in the face-sheet. The SB specimens failed by interlaminar shear fracture in the central portion of the specimens along layers that are contiguous with the embedded cells.

Figure 7 shows volume- and weight-normalized Ragone curves for SB composites. The data have been adjusted to account for the extended lengths of the fabricated specimens, given in Table 1. The extended lengths were implemented to satisfy bend test requirements (span-to-thickness ratio \rightarrow face-sheet failure). The data show the expected trend of decreasing energy storage capacity with increased discharge power level. The Modular SB Stiffener specimen (without skin) actually exceeds the targeted energy density of 50 Wh/L at the three lower discharge rates and meets the target at the 2C discharge rate. The other configurations do not quite meet the target even at the lower discharge rate (C/4). Measured volumetric energy capacity values at the 1C discharge rate for each SB are provided in Table 2.

DISCUSSION

The testing has shown that the SB specimens exhibit larger apparent bending stiffnesses than the unifunctional specimens. The SB Laminate and Modular SB Stiffener with Skin show stiffness values ~7.0x and 7.7x greater than the stiffness of the Unifunctional Laminate (Table 2). Obviously, the SB laminates are over-designed as replacements for a unifunctional laminate skin based on stiffness. The foam-cell frames in the multifunctional designs move the stiff-carbon reinforced layers out from the neutral axis, thus enhancing the bending stiffness. To better match the bending stiffness of the unifunctional laminate, we can decrease the number of carbon-epoxy layers in the SB laminates.

The SB Sandwich is 1.2x stiffer than that of the Uni-Sandwich, which is attributed to its slightly greater thickness. This is due to the non-uniform adhesive layer thickness in the SB Sandwich specimens (Figures 4 & 8). This occurred because the pre-cured face-sheets were slightly warped due to their non-symmetric lay-up [G-4C]. It can be prevented in the future through bonding procedures that account for face sheet warping or eliminated completely, we believe, using a new fabrication process with VARTM and co-curing of entire assemblies of SB components.

In the strength testing, the SB sandwich specimens failed at only ~43% of the uni-sandwich failure load. The nominally 12 mm thick SAN foam cores of the SB and uni-sandwich specimens were comprised of three 4 mm thick foam layers adhesively bonded together. The cells in the SB sandwich were incorporated in the second (middle) foam layer, and it was decided to use similar construction (i.e., three 4 mm thick layers rather than one 12 mm thick layer) for uni-sandwich so that we could clearly see the

affect of adding cells on the mechanical performance. Failure in the SB sandwich specimens occurred by interlaminar fracture of the non-uniform adhesive layer between the first and second foam layers, and failure in the uni-sandwich occurred by face-sheet compression overload (Figure 8). The change in failure mode between the SB and uni-sandwich specimens is clearly due to the presence of the embedded cells and/or the non-uniform adhesive layer thickness.

The SB Laminate specimens failed at ~44% of the failure load of the Modular SB Stiffener with Skin specimens. The failure mode in both configurations was again interlaminar fracture (Figure 8) along planes contiguous with the flat face-sheets and the cell layer. The SB Modular specimens failed at the adhesive layer joining the “skin” to the “stiffener.” The SB Laminate specimens failed at the bond between the flat and the conformal layers.

Consider the role of the embedded cells in the consistent interlaminar fracture modes of failure in the SB specimens. Lithium polymer cells are comprised of multiple layers of active battery material packaged in a thin, multi-layer, heat-sealed laminate under vacuum. The degree of shear resistance the cells can offer depends on how the active material layers are stacked and bonded, on the degree of bonding between the active material mass and the packaging, and on the quality of the bond between the cell packaging and the composite into which it is embedded. In the Kokam cells, the active materials are joined in a “Z-Fold” configuration, that offers limited material continuity between layers (at the folds) for shear resistance. There is no chemical or adhesive bonding between the active material mass and the packaging, only mechanical friction under the vacuum load. The outer layer of the packaging is nylon, which does not generally bond well without treatment. The plasma etching of the cells followed by epoxy dip-coating prior to potting in the foam frames seems to achieve good bonding and load transfer from structure to/through the cells. It seems likely that the low shear resistance of the embedded cells is a major contributor to the interlaminar fracture failure modes of SB specimens. A re-evaluation of the location of the cells within the composite is necessary to determine the optimal placement for SB composite strength.

As was mentioned earlier, the energy density data provided in Figure 7 and Table 2 has been adjusted to correspond to a “unit-cell” value that does not include the added specimen lengths introduced for mechanical testing purposes. The Modular SB Stiffener with Skin comes close to meeting 50 Wh/L at the two lower discharge rates (C/4 & C/2) and exhibits the largest energy density of all the SB designs.

The electrical storage capacity of the SB specimens is very close to that calculated based on the pre-embedded cells. The ability to achieve a particular energy density in a SB design therefore depends solely on the ability to control the final volume of the SB composite. The targeted design energy density value was 50 Wh/L or greater in all SB specimens configurations. The fact that we did not meet this design target in the fabricated specimens can be attributed to the larger thicknesses occurring in the fabricated specimens relative to their design values. This is primarily due to not accounting for the adhesive layers in SB assemblies. If the design thicknesses for the SB specimens had been achieved, then 1C capacities would have been: 75 Wh/l, 59 Wh/l, 55 Wh/l and 51 Wh/l, for the Modular SB Stiffener without Skin, Modular SB Stiffener with Skin, Integrated SB Laminate and the SB Sandwich designs, respectively.

The data in Table 2 show that SB designs meet, or come close to meeting, three of the four objectives with a trade-off between thickness and buoyancy. That is, keeping the thickness of the SB composite identical to its unifunctional counterpart leads to a

decrease in its buoyancy. Conversely, if the buoyancy is kept the same, then the SB composite will have a larger thickness. The only way to satisfy all four objectives simultaneously is to use battery cells that possess identical mechanical and physical (density) properties as the structural material being replaced. Then, all mechanical and physical properties will be the same with an added electrical energy storage capability.

Design-wise, the modular SB design offers a key advantage over the integrated SB laminate design in being capable (potentially) of easy removal and replacement should problems arise with the embedded cells (e.g., at the end of cell life). The Modular SB Stiffener with Skin tested and described in this work utilized an irreversible adhesive bond (Spabond 345) to attach the skin to the stiffener. Efforts are ongoing to identify reversible attachment methods for easy removal and replacement capability.

Adding battery cells with wiring to composites significantly increases the time and complexity of the fabrication process. A big part of that is related to the temperature limitation on the cells (~60 deg C). Marine composites use lower temperature curing epoxies (e.g., 80 deg C), but even exposure at this temperature level can lead to degradation in energy storage capacity. As described in Salomon et al. [15], cell electrolytes with LiPF_6 begin to decompose at 80-85 deg C and can be volatilized, which produces cell “puffing”. In addition, the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) on the lithiated carbon electrode (anode) can breakdown at these temperatures allowing continuous reactions to occur that affect cell capacity. On the cathode, the SEI can grow in thickness, which increases the internal impedance and degrades the power delivery capability. Ultimately, short term exposure at 80-90 deg C during curing of the epoxies may be acceptable; cell capacity and safety testing at these temperatures with various states-of-charge is needed. The fabrication process can be significantly shortened if the cells can be co-cured with all composite components making up a particular SB design.

Several other design/fabrication issues needing future attention include the need for battery management circuitry to provide charge/discharge control for long cell life and safety reasons (particularly with serial connections), and water-tight electrical connections to the power-bussing exiting the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

Three types of multifunctional structure-battery (SB) marine composites have been designed, fabricated and characterized in this work. The results show that the SB composites provide electrical energy storage capacity while achieving comparable flexural stiffness and buoyancy values but some degradation in strength and slightly larger thicknesses relative to their unifunctional counterparts. Critical issues for future work include: improvements in strength, simplified fabrication, and improvements in power bussing and wiring connections.

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REFERENCES

1. Liu, P. Sherman, E., and Jacobsen, A., "Design and fabrication of multifunctional structural batteries," *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 189, No. 1, 2009, pp. 646-650.
2. Pereira, T., Scaffaro, R., Guo, Z., Nieh, S., Arias, J., and Hahn, H.T., "Performance of Thin-Film Lithium Energy Cells Under Uniaxial Pressure," *Advanced Engineering Materials*, Vol. 10, No. 4, 2008, pp. 393-399.
3. Pereira, T., Guo, Z., Nieh, S., Arias, J., and Hahn, H.T., "Embedding Thin-Film Lithium Energy Cells in Structural Composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 68, No. 7-8, 2008, pp. 1935-1941.
4. South, J.T., Carter, R.H., Snyder, J.F., Hilton, C.D., O'Brien, D.J., and Wetzel, E.D., "Multifunctional Power-Generating and Energy-Storing Structural Composites for U.S. Army Applications," *Proceedings of the Materials Research Society Symposium*, Vol. 851, MRS, Warrendale, PA, 2005, pp. 139-150.
5. Wong, E.L., Baechele, D.M., Xu, K., Carter, R.H., Snyder, J.F., and Wetzel, E.D., "Design and Processing of Structural Composite Batteries," *Proceedings of the International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition*, Vol. 52, SAMPE, Covina, CA, 2007, pp. 15.
6. Snyder, J.F., Carter, R.H., and Wetzel, E.D., "Electrochemical and Mechanical Behaviour in Mechanically Robust Solid Polymer Electrolytes for Use in Multifunctional Structural Batteries," *Chemistry of Materials*, Vol. 19, No. 15, 2007, pp. 3793-3801.
7. Snyder, J.F., Wong, E.L., and Hubbard, C.W., "Evaluation of Commercially Available Carbon Fibers, Fabrics, and Papers for Potential Use in Multifunctional Energy Storage Applications," *Journal of the Electromechanical Society*, Vol. 156, No. 3, 2009, pp. A215-A224.
8. Thomas, J.P., Qidwai, M.A., and Kellogg, J.C., "Energy scavenging for small-scale unmanned systems," *Journal of Power Sources*, Vol. 159, No. 2, 2006, pp. 1494-1509.
9. Pereira, T., Guo, Z., Nieh, S., Arias, J., and Hahn, H.T., "Integration of Thin-Film Solar and Energy Cells in Multifunctional Structural Composites for Energy Harvesting," *Proceedings of the International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition*, Vol. 52, SAMPE, Covina, CA, 2008, pp. 21.
10. Thomas, J.P., and Qidwai, M.A., "Mechanical Design and Performance of Composite Multifunctional Materials," *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 52, No. 8, 2004, pp. 2155-2164.
11. Thomas, J.P., and Qidwai, M.A., "The Design and Application of Multifunctional Structure-Battery Materials Systems," *JOM*, Vol. 57, No. 3, 2005, pp. 18-24.
12. Qidwai, M.A., Baucom, J.N., Thomas, J.P., and Horner, D.M., "Multifunctional Applications of Thin Film Li Polymer Battery Cells," *Materials Science Forum*, Vol. 492-493, 2005, pp. 157-162.

13. Pogue, W.R., Qidwai, M.A., Thomas, J.P., and Rohatgi, A., “Structure-Battery Composites for Marine Applications – Part I: Multifunctional Design and Fabrication”, SAMPE Fall Technical Conference Proceedings [CD-ROM], SAMPE, Covina, CA, 2008, pp. 25.
14. Rohatgi, A., Thomas, J.P., Qidwai, M.A., and Pogue, W.R., “Structure-Battery Composites for Marine Applications - Part II: Multifunctional Performance Characterization”, SAMPE Fall Technical Conference Proceedings [CD-ROM], SAMPE, Covina, CA, 2008, pp. 18.
15. Soloman, M., Lin,, H.-P., Plichta, E. J., and Hendrickson, M., “Temperature Effects on Li-Ion Cell Performance”, in *Advances in Lithium-Ion Batteries*, W. van Schalkwijk and B. Scrosati, Eds., Kluwer Academic/Plenum Publishers, New York, 2002, pp. 309-344.

Table 1: Dimensions of fabricated specimens.

Name	Average Dimensions (mm)				
	Length	Width		Thickness	
		Top	Bottom	Overall	Side Edge
Integrated SB laminate	435	80	100	9.6	4.4
Laminate	415	100		4.26	
Modular SB Stiffener (No Skin)	436	80	90	7.8	2.9
Modular SB Stiffener (w/ Skin)	436 (415*)	80	100*	9.9	1.4*
SB Sandwich	406	80		20.8	17.9
Sandwich	385	80		18.71	

* represents skin dimensions (i.e. the laminate bonded to the bottom of Modular SB Stiffener).

Table 2: Comparison of experimentally measured properties.

Parameter	Uni Laminate	Integrated SB Laminate	Modular SB Stiffener	Modular SB Stiffener with Skin	Uni Sandwich	SB Sandwich
Bending Stiffness, $(EI)_{app}$ (N-m ²)	28.3±0.5	199±11	41.2±1.1	219±6	840±46	985±31
Bending Failure Load, P_{bf} (N)	1300 & 1270	2110 & 2090	not tested	4800 & 4680	12710 & 11760	5500 & 5070
Energy Density @1C (Wh/L) [†]	0	42.3	58.1	42.8	0	41.7
Mass Density (kg/m ³)	1534	1303	1331	1334	727	1142
Thickness (mm)	4.3	9.6	7.8	10.2	20.0	20.8

[†] The energy density data has been adjusted to account for extended length introduced in the specimens to satisfy bending test requirements (i.e., “Length Corrected Values”).

Figure 1: End cross-section views of the SB Laminate (top), Modular SB Stiffener with Skin (middle), and the SB sandwich (bottom) composite specimens.

Figure 2: End and top views of a SB Laminate specimen showing the battery terminal strips at each end. The bottom layer is flat and the top layer is conformal.

Figure 3: Bottom view of a Modular SB Stiffener specimen before it is bonded with a thin laminate skin showing two Kokam cells wired (internally) in parallel (Left). Top view of a Modular SB Stiffener with Skin (Right).

Figure 4: Side and top views of a SB Sandwich specimen. Note the non-uniform adhesive layer thickness (pink) shown in the side view.

Figure 5: Representative load-displacement curves for the Unifunctional Laminate and the Modular SB Stiffener with Skin. The “triangle” in each plot indicates the displacement range used in the least squares fittings for the slope.

Figure 6: Load-displacement curves during strength testing of the laminate (left) and sandwich (right) specimen configurations. The Uni-Laminate specimens did not fail.

Figure 7: Length corrected Ragone curves of parallel-connected embedded cells (in SB specimens). The axes in the left hand side plot are normalized by the specimen volume, and weight in the right hand side plot. The targeted energy density goal of 50 Wh/L is indicated by a dash line.

Figure 8: Photos of representative strength testing specimens post-test showing the failure modes for each type of specimen. The SB composites failed by interlaminar fracture along planes contiguous with the embedded cells. The Unifunctional Sandwich failed by compressive fracture of the carbon-epoxy face-sheet, at the center of the bend fixture at the edge of the load spreader pad.